

MARKETING IN THE FOOTBALL CLUB SYSTEM

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Abstract. This article examines the significant role that marketing has played in the transformation of football from a regional sport to a global phenomenon. It delves into the key marketing strategies employed by clubs, leagues, and governing bodies to build brand identity, expand reach, promote player development, drive revenue, and foster positive social impact. The article concludes by highlighting the enduring influence of marketing on the sport's trajectory and its continued relevance in a rapidly evolving global landscape.

Keywords: Football, Marketing, Brand Identity, Fan Engagement, Global Reach, Player Development, Revenue Generation, Social Impact, Sports Industry.

FUTBOL KLUBI TIZIMIDA MARKETING

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada marketing futbolning mintaqaviy sport turidan global hodisaga aylanishida qanday muhim rol o'ynaganini ko'rib chiqadi. U klublar, ligalar va boshqaruv organlari tomonidan brend identifikatorini shakllantirish, ta'sir doirasini kengaytirish, o'yinchilarni rivojlantirish, daromadlarni oshirish va ijobiy ijtimoiy ta'sirni kuchaytirish uchun qo'llaniladigan asosiy marketing strategiyalarini o'rganadi. Maqolaning yakunida marketingning sport traektoriyasiga doimiy ta'siri va uning tez rivojlanayotgan global landshaftdagi dolzarbligi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: Futbol, marketing, brend identifikatori, muxlislar ishtiroki, global ta'sir, o'yinchilarni rivojlantirish, daromad olish, ijtimoiy ta'sir, sport sanoati.

Introduction

Marketing for Football Clubs

Football clubs have millions of fans worldwide and are more than just sports teams.

Football clubs utilise marketing to increase fan loyalty, make money from sponsorships and retail sales, and establish their brand globally. In order to engage with supporters and keep the club relevant both during and outside of the season, tactics including producing original content, running social media campaigns, and holding brand activations are essential.

Clubs like Real Sociedad use their mascot on social media, while Leganés is known for creative advertisements. Manchester City has launched a TikTok account specifically for the American market, expanding its reach. FC Barcelona uses immersive experiences and AR technology globally, and Juventus promotes documentaries on streaming platforms, strengthening the emotional bond with fans.

Marketing in World Cups and International Competitions

Global competitions such as the FIFA World Cup provide enormous opportunities for sports advertising. Here, the main goals are to maximise worldwide visibility, draw in well-known sponsors, and provide fans experiences they won't soon forget. In addition to capturing the thrill of the occasion, marketing efforts for these contests need to develop a story that appeals to viewers around the world and in many cultural contexts. To accomplish these goals, technology, narrative, and social media interaction are essential instruments.

Marketing for Players

World-famous football players, in particular, are brands unto themselves. Building their public profile, controlling their social media accounts, and landing sponsorship agreements that complement their personalities with the appropriate businesses are the main goals of player marketing. This covers everything, from producing original content to taking part in international marketing initiatives. For a player's career on the pitch as well as their business prospects off it, image management is essential.

The Internet has developed into a business environment and a highly demanding distribution channel over time. Consequently, internet marketing—which involves using the Internet for promotional purposes—is becoming more and more well-liked [5].

There is no doubt that the development of social media had a great influence on the changes in the nature of marketing used by football clubs. A study by Euromerica Sport Marketing showed that approximately 82% of the most remembered ads in social media are those with athletes [6].

Leo Messi's posts rank seventh and ninth, respectively, while Cristiano Ronaldo's is already in second place. This may come as a surprise because, until recently, athletes were not as closely linked to the media as influencers or music stars. It is important to remember that a football player's popularity can significantly increase the popularity of the team he plays for. A formidable rival emerged when Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter dominated the online advertising space. Football teams are now using the TikTok app as a relatively new marketing tool.

Marketing departments soon discovered how widely used this medium has become, so they do not limit themselves to publishing live matches, behind-the-scenes videos or interviews.

The Parisian club is clearly the most popular among TikTok users. A true marketing success is having more than 23.2 million followers (Fig. 1). According to these figures, the top 10 clubs in this ranking and the top 10 clubs that sell club shirts nearly exactly match. This demonstrates their great emphasis on marketing success and their multifaceted approach to achieving it.

Players like Neymar and Messi have started their own apparel companies in addition to working with premium and fashion labels. Through their platforms, they also support charitable endeavours, improving their reputation and aiding important causes.

Figure 1. Top 3 most followed football clubs on Tik Tok in 2022 (Foot Goal, n.d.). [7]

1. Building Brand Identity and Fan Loyalty. Football clubs and leagues have meticulously cultivated distinctive brand identities through a variety of marketing strategies. Iconic logos, vibrant mascots, and captivating narratives contribute to creating a sense of belonging and pride among supporters. The enduring power of these elements is evident in the passionate followings of clubs like Manchester United, Real Madrid, and Barcelona. Social media platforms have further enhanced fan engagement, allowing clubs to connect with supporters, share content, and foster a sense of community.

2. Expanding Global Reach and Fan Base. Marketing has been instrumental in expanding football's reach beyond its traditional boundaries. Internationalization strategies, driven by partnerships and global broadcasting deals, have captivated new audiences worldwide. The English Premier League, for instance, has successfully established a global fanbase through its strategic marketing efforts. Furthermore, the use of social media platforms has allowed clubs and leagues to connect with fans across continents, breaking down geographical barriers.

3. Promoting Player Development and Talent Acquisition: Marketing has played a vital role in nurturing young talent and creating future stars. Clubs invest heavily in youth academies, developing players from a young age. Strategic marketing campaigns, coupled with player endorsements and social media presence, build up the image and popularity of players, turning them into global icons and attracting attention to the sport.

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